

REPORT FOR PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURES' SINGLE RISK AND FLOOD RISK ANALYSIS MAP OF NINE WEST ATHENS MUNICIPALITIES

A. Introduction, Description and Data Analysis Process

This report is the result of the actions carried out mainly during the second period of SOTERIA, in order to complete the program requirements and the required activities connected with the indicators (KPI'S) of the WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 packages. Initially, it should be mentioned that from the research and study process carried out both during the first and second period, it was observed that there are no insurance contracts that specifically cover damage from heat waves. This is because damage cannot be directly linked to high temperatures.

For this reason, it was considered that a modification should be made to the initial position of the case study for the proposal and implementation of a heatwave insurance policy in the risk mapping of a series of properties/locations in West Athens, such as city halls and schools, and in the flood risk analysis mapping for the nine municipalities. The aim was to assess the natural hazards that are most likely to occur in West Athens, as well as the areas that are most at risk of flooding.

Based on this assessment, an action plan was drawn up, proposing policies for protection and prevention from natural hazards that are most likely to damage public infrastructure in West Athens. A classification for local protection projects, flood protection projects at the municipal level and projects at the inter-municipal level is also proposed. Based on this direction, a model insurance contract was proposed for risks such as fires, floods, wildfires, snowfall, earthquakes, etc.

In summary, the process included the following stages:

- Contacting the municipalities to send coordinates, square meters per floor and type of construction (metal construction or reinforced concrete) for the town hall of each municipality and two schools of their choice. The main selection criteria were the number and age of children, the "dangerousness" of the area and the condition of the buildings. Table 1 shows the schools of choice for each municipality. The data was sent with a protocol so that these data could be published.

- Data entry by Dionysis Matsas in the special HDI ARGOS 4.0 application developed by the HDI insurance company.

-Extracting a single analysis risk map for public infrastructure and a flood risk analysis map for each municipality (<https://zenodo.org/records/19108604>). The single analysis risk map extracts the degree of exposure of each public infrastructure to the following risks: a. Earthquake, b. Snow Load, c. Extra Tropical Storm, d. Volcanic Ash, e. Tornado, f. Hail, g. Lighting, h. Flood, i. Landslide, k. Tropical Cyclone, l. Tsunami, m. Storm Surge and n. Volcano. The flood risk analysis was based on the spread, duration, rise in water level, the probability of recurrence of flooding in the following years, the location and the relief of the landscape. The level of rise in water level is indicated by the color difference of the waters. The main causes of flooding are mapped while three levels of flood risk can be identified, low, medium and high.

- Statistical analysis for an overall presentation of the probability of occurrence of natural hazards in public infrastructures. The probability of occurrence was presented in relation to the type of infrastructure and the municipality. The program assigned a risk value to the exposure of each infrastructure for 13 natural hazards. The rating values were five, starting from the value 'no exposure', continuing with the values 'very low', 'low', 'moderate' ending with the value 'high'. The values were rated starting from 0 as the lowest value reaching 4 as the highest exposure value. Mean values and standard deviations were calculated for each natural hazard in total, as well as their means for each infrastructure and each municipality. The higher the mean value is interpreted as a greater probability of exposure to the natural hazard.

A, Selected Schools by the Municipalities			
Schools	Municipality	Schools	Municipality
1 st High School	Agia Varvara	7 th junior high	Korydallos
1 st Primary School	Agia Varvara	2 nd high EPAL School	Peristeri
2 nd Primary School	Agioi Anargyroi	12 th primary School	Peristeri
High School	Agioi Anargyroi	2 nd primary school	Petroupoli
6 th High School	Xaidari	9 th primary school	Petroupoli
2 ND High School	Xaidarii	2 ND Primary & Kindergarten	Aigaleo

19 TH Primary School	Aigaleo	2 nd High School	Fyli
6h primary school	Fyli	1 st High School	Ilion
4 th junior high school	Ilion		

B. Single Risk Map Analysis's results of Municipalities' Public Infrastructures

As can be seen from **table b**, the natural hazards that most threaten public infrastructure declared by municipalities are mainly earthquakes, secondarily "snow load", "extra tropical storm", "volcanic ash" and finally "tornado", "hail", "lightning", and "floods". Based on the overall average values as derived from the single map analysis, the risk of damage from natural hazards such as "landslide", "tropical cyclone", "tsunami", "storm surge" and "volcano" is negligible.

B. Means and standard deviations of risks for all public infrastructure in the nine municipalities		
Hazards	Means	Standard Deviations
Earthquake	4.00	0.00
Snow Load	2.96	0.20
Extra Tropical Storm	2.92	0.40
Volcanic Ash	2.00	0,00
Tornado	1.92	0.28
Hail	1.84	0.47
Lighting	1.12	0.44
Flood	0.80	1.32
Landslide	0.16	0.37
Tropical Cyclone	0.12	0.60
Tsounami	0.04	0.20
Storm Surge	0.00	0.00

As we can see in **Table D**, the schools are more likely to be damaged by “snow load”, “extra tropical storm”, and “hail” than the town halls. The town halls are more likely to be damaged by “lightning” than the schools, while the s primary schools are more likely to be damaged by “windstorm” and “hail” than the secondary schools and town halls.

D. Means for different public infrastructures for each hazard seperately			
Hazards	Townhalls	Primary Schools	High Schools
Earthquake	4,00	4,00	4,00
Snow Load	2,89	3,00	3,00
Extra Tropical Storm	2,78	3,00	3,00
Volcanic Ash	2,00	2,00	2,00
Tornado	1,89	2,00	1,83
Hail	1,78	1,90	1,83
Lighting	1,22	1,00	1,17
Flood	0,56	0,60	1,50
Landslide	0,00	0,40	0,00
Tropical Cyclone	0,33	0,00	0,00
Tsounami	0,11	0,00	0,00

Storm Surge	0,00	0,00	0,00
Volcano	0,00	0,00	0,00

Γ. Flood risk map analysis' results for nine municipalities

As can be seen from **Table E**, three main causes of flood risk can be observed that are “repeated” in different ways and for different areas of the nine municipalities. It should be noted that the frequency distribution was made considering the “high risk” causes for the areas corresponding to each municipality, without meaning that in these municipalities’ different causes of flood, medium or low risk, may coexist.

One of the main causes of high flood risk is the overflow of the Kifissos or old streams.

In the area of Agioi Anargyroi, the high-risk points are identified along the railway lines that follow the course of Kifisos, as well as at the intersections and bridges over the river and in the lower-lying areas, which are vulnerable to river overtopping.

A lower risk level is observed across the wider urban road network of the area, where water depth is typically shallower, usually below 0.5 m. However, flooding is extensive, making roads impassable.

In Fyli, high flood risk areas are located in Ano Liosia, near the streams of Eschatia, facing a significant risk of damage to buildings and public infrastructures, situated directly in the water flow path. The central part of Ano Liosia, near Attiki Odos, is also exposed to high flood risk. In this zone, run off descending rapidly from the mountain encounters flatter terrain, resulting in ponding. This phenomenon creates flood basins that affect entire building blocks and make roads impassable.

The area of Chasia can be classified as a medium flood risk area. Water behaves as a torrent, carrying stones and wood, increasing the hazard consequences, even when the water depth appears relatively shallow.

Neighborhoods located in Ano Liosia, “upstream” of Attiki Odos, may experience a sudden rise in water level if the drainage conduits become clogged by "material" brought by the water.

A similar pattern is observed in Ilion central and southern sectors, where high flood risk arises due to the flat topography, which enhances water accumulation. There is a particularly high risk for ground-floor dwellings, business and basements. In the eastern part of the municipality, which borders Agioi Anargyroi, local waterflows converges. When Kifisos is at a high-water level, drainage from Ilion is blocked, resulting in the water overflow.

There is a high risk of flooding in the neighborhoods near Antonis Tritsis Park, on the borders with Kamatero and Agioi Anargyroi because the park functions as a natural relief area and are affected by the overflow of the networks.

Finally, the areas around Agiou Fanouriou and Idomeneos Street could be categorized as medium to low flood risk areas. These zones follow the alignment of former streams that have been channeled or covered by roads. In the event of flooding, these corridors are transformed into fast-flowing torrents. In such cases, the velocity of the water poses an equally significant hazard as the water depth itself.

In the Municipality of Aigaleo, areas located near Eastern Aigaleo, and National Road, such as the neighborhoods bordering Peristeri and Renti could be categorized as high flood risk areas. They are at risk of serious damage to basements, ground floors and infrastructure, due to the overflow of the river.

The areas near Iera odos or Thivon face a medium or low risk of flooding because they act as "rivers" that carry water rapidly towards Kifisos. The speed of the water is the greatest risk for pedestrians and vehicles.

"Flash floods" caused by torrents and rapid flow occur less frequently. For example, in Peristeri, the neighborhoods that border the National Road and follow the Kifissos River direction are at risk of flooding, such as the area around the Rossignol Bridge or Athens Avenue, running the greatest risk of serious material damage to buildings and public infrastructure. Similarly, areas with dense construction or near major road junctions, such as the area around Thivon or near Agios Antonios Metro station, are also at high risk of flooding.

Areas that follow old streams that have now been covered by roads are also at high risk. During extreme rainfall, these roads "become" rivers again, carrying water at high speed towards Kifissos.

In Haidari, due to its location at the foot of Mount Egaleo, the risk does not come from water concentrated in large areas, but from the rapid flow towards the lower areas. There are specific points, especially near intersections and in places where the slope of the ground changes abruptly. There the water accumulates, resulting in a significant increase in depth. These points are the most vulnerable to flooding in ground-floor shops and underground garages.

In the areas of West Haidari, towards Skaramanga, which follow the natural ravines, the risk is more localized but very intense due to the morphology, with the possibility of transporting soil and stones from the slopes.

The areas around Chaidari Forest and near large complexes (such as Attikon Hospital) concentrate flows around the perimeter of the facilities. In this way, while the buildings may be at safe heights, the entrance gates and access roads are often located within the blue zones, which can make access difficult in cases of emergency.

Finally, an example in this direction concerns Korydallos areas where the water deepens “dangerously” in “squares” or “intersections” creating a risk of flooding in ground-floor shops and underground garages. Large open areas, such as around the prison complex or sports facilities, are surrounded by “flood risk zones”, leading to the concentration of water in the lowest-altitude perimeter roads, effectively cutting off access to these infrastructures during intense phenomena.

The parts of Korydallos that are higher are considered the source of water runoff and for this reason do not face a risk of flooding. The risk of flooding is medium or low for the areas that cross the city from the northwest to the southeast because the central roads of Korydallos function as natural drains for the water coming from the mountain. The water does not simply stagnate, but moves at high speed. The danger here mainly concerns the drifting of vehicles and the difficulty of pedestrian movement.

Flash floods that result in the water accumulation in "natural basins" occur less frequently in the nine municipalities.

For example, in Agia Varvara which are located on the border of the region with Egaleo, close to central road axes (such as Megalou Alexandrou or El. Venizelou), the relief becomes flatter, resulting in water that comes down from the higher areas stagnating.

In these points, the depth of the water increases, increasing the risk for ground-floor and underground shops or residences.

The source of the water runoff could be argued to be the areas of the West part of the hill which are not at risk of flooding since they are located on the edges of the mountain. For example, Petroupoli areas located on the border with Ilion where the ground begins to level off, the speed of the water decreases and accumulation begins (stagnant water). The ground floors and basements on these lower "borders" of Petroupoli are at greater risk of flooding.

A medium risk of flooding is observed for the areas from the west (mountain) to the east (towards Ilion/Peristeri), especially in the urban fabric, following the flow of rainwater on the streets. Because the slope is high, the water acquires high speed. The danger here is not the depth, but the force of the water that can carry away objects or make the crossing of pedestrians dangerous.

Most of the residential areas of Petroupoli are at low risk of flooding, especially at higher elevations (towards Petra Theatre and the foothills of the mountain). Due to the altitude, there is no risk of "stagnant" water. The likelihood of a house being flooded by standing water in these areas is extremely low.

E. Flood Risk Analysis		
Causes of Flooding	F & F%	Municipalities
Overflow of Kifissos or old streams	4/44, 4%	Agioi Anargyroi Ilion Fyli Aigaleo
Flash floods from rapid flow and torrents	3/33, 3%	Korydalos Peristeri Chaidari
Flash floods, concentration in natural basins	2/22, 2%	Agia Varvara Petroupoli

D. Proposed Action Plan

The risk analysis carried out for the twenty-five public buildings, city halls and selected schools, in the nine West Athens' municipalities clearly shows which natural hazards 'offer' the greatest opportunities for insurance.

Earthquake is the dominant risk, as it presents the highest exposure value in all buildings and in all municipalities without exception. Snow load and extra tropical storm follow, which show a high probability in eight of the nine municipalities, with particularly increased values in schools compared to city halls.

Then, significant exposures are created by secondary perils like tornado, hail and lightning. Particularly high values for snow, storm, tornado and hail are recorded in primary schools, while Agia Varvara presents comparatively lower values for some of these risks.

Floods, despite having a low average exposure value for all public infrastructure, 'create' significant picks of risk in specific areas. The municipalities with the highest flood exposures are Ilion, Aigaleo, Fyli, Peristeri and Chaidari. In these areas, the risk comes mainly from the overflow of the Kifissos River, the rapid flow of torrents such as Eschatia, as well as from stagnant water in flat basins. Water stagnates for many hours in low-lying areas of Ilion and Aigaleo, while in Fyli and Chaidari the rapid flow from the mountain and the concentration of water due to Attiki Odos create strong pressures on roads, ground floors, basements and schools.

In Peristeri, neighborhoods near the National Road and in old streams that have been covered by roads face a high risk of material damage and cut-off of access.

Based on the above, the action plan proposes a series of immediate and practical measures that can be initiated immediately by municipalities:

- Initially, within the first few months, priority should be given to the complete cleaning and regular maintenance of all drainage pipes, culverts and natural streams, in order to avoid blockage and overflow during heavy rainfall.
- At the same time, it is necessary to widely and systematically inform citizens who reside or work in high-risk zones, through targeted campaigns, brochures, digital applications and local meetings, so that they are aware of dangerous points, evacuation routes and basic self-protection actions.

- - The most important first step is the immediate establishment of the Inter-Municipal Risk Management Committee through ASDA, which will function as a common coordinating body of all nine municipalities, ensuring a unified policy and rapid decision-making.
- Subsequently, the plan provides for the implementation of targeted flood control projects at both the local and inter-municipal levels, such as the construction of small retention tanks, the elevation of critical road sections and the creation of green absorption zones.
- At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen coordination between the technical services of the municipalities, by developing a common communication protocol, creating an inter-municipal business center and jointly purchasing necessary equipment. An important role is also played by the mandatory technical evaluation of all buildings located in risk zones, especially ground floors and basements, as well as the establishment of a financial subsidy program for individuals, so that they can proceed with simple but effective anti-flood interventions in their homes and businesses.
- Finally, it is proposed to introduce an Insurance Solution to mitigate such climate risk exposures and comprehensively cover the main / dominant perils, such as earthquake, wildfires, flood, snow load and storms, for both public infrastructure and private property.

The financing of all the above actions can be secured through the available European and national programs, such as ESPA, the Recovery Fund and the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan. Public infrastructure and priority public projects could be selected as resulting from the report and an inter-municipal competition could be announced for the submission of insurance offers. The insurance contracts within the framework of this specific procedure could be based on the original contract for symbolic disasters created within the framework of the participation of the case study of Western Athens in SOTERIA (<https://zenodo.org/records/19109258>).

In any case, the immediate establishment and activation of the Inter-Municipal Risk Management Committee is the first and most basic step, as without an organized and coordinated framework of cooperation between the municipalities it will be difficult to

achieve substantial protection of public infrastructure, the road network and private property, while at the same time significantly strengthening the overall resilience of the entire Western Athens against natural hazards. The organizational role of the ASDA in this direction is decisive.